

Banu Priya G M^{1*} and Doreswamy C²^{1*} M. Sc. (Agri.) Scholar, Department of Sericulture

UAS, GKVK, Bengaluru – 560 065

priyagowda366@gmail.com²Professor of Sericulture and Special officer

College of Agriculture, Haradanahalli Farm, Chamarajanagara – 571 127

drcdoreswamy@gmail.com

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Abstract

Study on the effect of legume mulching on growth, yield and quality of tree mulberry was carried out during the year 2021 at KVK, V. C. Farm, Mandya. Significantly higher plant height (281.40 cm), shoot length (190.53 cm), number of shoots plant⁻¹ (25.60), number of leaves plant⁻¹ (391.93) and leaf yield (83.42 tons ha⁻¹ year⁻¹) were recorded in tree mulberry plot incorporated with black gram crop residue over non mulched plot. Quality parameters viz., leaf nitrogen content (4.28 %), phosphorous content (0.56 %), potassium content (2.93 %), sulphur content (0.85 %) and crude protein content (26.60 %) were registered higher in black gram residue incorporated plot whereas, calcium and magnesium contents (1.28 % and 0.68 %, respectively) were found to be higher in cowpea residue incorporated tree mulberry plot over plot without mulching. Rearing parameters of double hybrid silkworm viz., fifth day of fifth instar larval weight (41.73 g/10 larvae), cocoon weight (26.01 g/10 cocoons), pupal weight (19.69 g/10 pupae), cocoon shell weight (6.12 g/10 shells), cocoon shell ratio (23.53 %), single cocoon filament length (1277.17 m) and filament denier (3.53) were recorded significantly higher in case of tree mulberry plot incorporated with black gram residue over control.

Key words: Mulching, Tree Mulberry, Black gram, Silkworm, Denier

Introduction

Mulberry (*Morus alba* L.) is the only sole food for the silkworm (*Bombyx mori* L.) and also considered as an important perennial cash crop. The nutritive quality of mulberry leaf plays a vital role on the growth and development of silkworm as well as on the cocoon yield and quality of silk. The main advantage of growing leguminous cover crops in mulberry is to improve quality and quantity of leaf, preventing soil erosion, addition of organic matter, aeration and water retention capacity, weed check besides improving soil microbial activity. Purohit *et al.* (1992) have also tested certain Phyto mulches and found them very useful to Influences the soil temperature and moisture besides the growth and yield in mulberry under rain fed conditions of West Bengal. The effects of an organic approach to the use of legume cover crops and banana biomat (i.e., chopped or winged banana leaves or hulls) on plant growth, yield, and fruit quality and benefit: cost ratio of guava cultivation was found significant compared with the use of plastic mulch and conventional practices, viz., no use of organic mulch and cover crop (Bhattacharjee *et al.*, 2020).

Material And Methods

A study was conducted in a four year old well established V-1 tree mulberry garden at a spacing of 4 x 4 feet under irrigated condition during 2020-2021. The experiment was performed using a randomized complete block design consisting of seven treatments with three replicates. After top pruning, legume intercrops viz., rice bean, cowpea, blackgram, greengram, horse gram and field bean were sown in the space between the rows of tree mulberry. Package of practices for both tree mulberry and intercrops were followed as per the recommended standards. Legumes plants were incorporated into the respective plot after the harvest of the pods.

Treatment details:T₁ - Tree mulberry + Rice beanT₂ - Tree mulberry + CowpeaT₃ - Tree mulberry + Black gramT₄ - Tree mulberry + Green gramT₅ - Tree mulberry + Horse gramT₆ - Tree mulberry + Field beanT₇ - Sole tree mulberry (control – without mulching)

The observations on various growth parameters viz., plant height, shoot length, number of shoots plant⁻¹, number of leaves plant⁻¹ and leaf yield were recorded at 60 Days after Pruning. Quality parameters

viz., leaf nitrogen, phosphorous, potassium, crude protein, calcium and magnesium and sulphur were recorded at 45 Days after Pruning.

Nutrient analysis of tree mulberry leaves

Leaf nitrogen, phosphorous, potassium, calcium and magnesium estimated by Kjeldahl's digestion and distillation, diacid digestion and colorimetry using vanadomolybdate reagent, Flame photometry, Complexometry using versenate solution, respectively as suggested by Piper (1966) and sulphur was estimated by Turbidometry method (Page *et al.*, 1982).

Estimation of crude protein (%)

Sample was digested with concentrated sulphuric acid in the presence of catalyst. The digested sample was distilled in the presence of NaOH and the liberated NH₃ was absorbed in boric acid. The content of NH₃ absorbed was determined by titrating against standard acid. Protein per cent was calculated by multiplying the nitrogen content with the factor 6.25.

Crude protein (%)

$$= \frac{\text{Titre value} \times N \text{ of sulphuric acid} \times 0.014 \times 6.25}{\text{Weight of sample (g)}} \times 100$$

Silkworm rearing

The commercial bivoltine double hybrid, Krishnaraja [FC1 (CSR6 x CSR 26) x FC2 (CSR2 x CSR 27)] was used in the study. The chawki worms were procured from the registered Chawki rearing centre, Mandya for the experiment. The chawki worms were reared in a paper boat, 50 worms were maintained per treatment per replication. Feeding is given three times a day (8.00 AM, 2.00 PM and 8.00 PM) with leaves of respective treatments. Bed cleaning was done two times each in IV and V instar by lifting the uneaten, left-over leaves from the paper boat.

Rearing performance of double hybrid silkworm FC1 x FC2

Fifth instar larval weight (g)

Weight of 10 larvae was recorded on fifth day of fifth instar in all the treatments of each replication and mean was computed.

Cocoon weight (g)

After the cocoon harvest, ten cocoons from each treatment with respective replications were randomly selected and the mean cocoon weight was computed.

Cocoon shell weight (g)

The 10 cocoon shells weight was recorded, after removing the pupa and last larval skin (exuvium) from the cocoon.

Pupal weight (g)

After obtaining the cocoon weight, same cocoons were cut open and pupal weight was taken.

Cocoon shell ratio (%)

The cocoon shell ratio percentage was calculated by the formula

$$\text{shell ratio (\%)} = \frac{\text{weight of ten cocoon shells (g)}}{\text{weight of ten cocoons (g)}} \times 100$$

Single cocoon filament length (m)

Ten cocoons were randomly selected from three replication of each treatment were reeled using epprouvette. Number of revolutions were recorded and converted into meters by the formula,

$$L = R \times 1.125$$

Where, L = total filament length (m/cocoon)

R = number of revolutions

1.125 = circumference of epprouvette

Denier

The raw silk filament was taken out from the epprouvette and was dried using hot air oven at 70 °C to 80 °C and weighed to determine the denier using the standard formula.

$$\text{Denier} = \frac{\text{weight of single cocoon filament (g)}}{\text{length of single cocoon filament (g)}} \times 9000$$

Where, 9000 = constant value

Results And Discussion

Growth and yield parameters of tree mulberry

Mulching of different legumes in tree mulberry shown significant differences were noticed on growth at 45 and 60 DAP, yield parameters at 60 DAP (Table 1 & 2).

The higher plant height (255.80 and 281.40 cm), shoot length (167.60 and 190.53 cm), number of shoots plant⁻¹ (23.87 and 25.60), number of leaves plant⁻¹ (295.47 and 391.93) at 45 and 60 DAP, respectively and leaf yield (83.42 tons ha⁻¹ year⁻¹) were registered in tree mulberry plot incorporated with residues of black gram. Whereas the lowest plant height, shoot length, number of shoots plant⁻¹, number of leaves plant⁻¹ and leaf yield (211.53 and 237.80 cm), (132.60 and 158.87 cm), (19.07 and 20.93), (212.07 and 356.40) and 50.39 tons ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, respectively were recorded in tree mulberry plot without mulching. The results are also in line with the findings of Chanchal *et al.* (2020), who reported that, maximum plant height of 93.66 cm was recorded in turmeric plot mulched with soybean straw over control (80.25 cm) where no mulching was taken. Similar results were also reported by the findings of Mir *et al.* (2015) who reported that, the maximum shoot length was recorded in mulberry plot with paddy grass mulch compared to the control. This may be due to the reduced weed population and increased nutrient availability. This may be due to the suppression of weed growth, better water holding capacity, improved soil structure, higher status of nutrient in soil and well development of root system.

Nutrient status of tree mulberry leaves

N, P, K, S and crude protein contents were significantly influenced in tree mulberry leaves after mulching (Table 3). Tree mulberry leaf mulched with black gram residues have recorded higher nitrogen, crude protein, phosphorous, potassium and sulphur (4.28 %, 26.60 %, 0.56 %, 2.93 % and 0.85 % respectively) over control. Higher calcium and magnesium contents of 1.28 and 0.68 per cent, respectively was noticed in cowpea residue mulched plot over without mulching plot. The results are supported by the findings of Das *et al.* (1990) who reported that, green manuring with cowpea, horse gram and dry weed mulches increased the total mulberry leaf nitrogen by 17.9, 22.2 and 9.8 per cent, respectively over control. The current study is supported by Nagesh (2002) who reported that, calcium, magnesium and sulphur contents of mulberry significantly higher when 100 per cent recommended nutrients were applied through green manure (2.826, 0.512 and 0.341 %, respectively) compared to control (without mulch). This might be due to the improvement of organic matter of soil by decomposition of applied mulches. Further, these organics might have increased the solubility of the insoluble native nutrients by means of releasing organic acids during the course of

decomposition which in turn helps in higher uptake of nutrients from the soil.

Rearing performance of double hybrid silkworm FC1 x FC2

Fifth instar larval weight (g), cocoon weight (g) and pupal weight (g)

Mulching of different legumes in tree mulberry garden have significantly influenced the performance of silkworm. Significantly higher larval, cocoon and pupal weight of silkworm was recorded in black gram residues mulched treatment (41.73 g/10, 26.01 g/10 and 19.69 g/10, respectively) followed by green gram residues mulched plot. Whereas, least weights were recorded in plot without any mulch (Table 4).

Cocoon shell weight (g), shell ratio (%), filament length (m) and denier

Performance of double hybrid silkworm was significantly influenced by legumes residues mulching (Table 5). Significantly higher cocoon shell weight, shell ratio, filament length and denier (6.12 g/10, 23.53 %, 1277.17 m and 3.53, respectively) was recorded in silkworms fed with leaves of tree mulberry plot mulched with black gram residues over control. The results are in agreement with the findings of Shashidhar *et al.* (2009) who recorded maximum larval weight, cocoon weight, single shell weight when silkworm fed with mulberry grown by mulching of paddy straw and compared to no mulched plots. The current study was supported by Sahida (2015), who recorded comparatively higher denier of 2.87 in silkworms fed with mulberry leaves raised with dry weed mulching. It may be due to organic mulch applied to mulberry might have increased the moisture and nutrient content in leaves which in turn influenced the silkworm growth, cocoon and silk quality parameters.

Conclusion

This study revealed that mulching of different legumes in tree mulberry garden enhanced the growth, yield and quality parameters of tree mulberry as well as silkworm performance. Among the different legume mulching, tree mulberry mulched with black gram recorded better performance in both tree mulberry and silkworm over sole cropping. The application of mulch had a beneficial effect on plant growth by altering the soil environment by maintaining a favourable temperature, increasing soil moisture retention for longer period, suppression of weed growth, improved soil structure, enough supply of organic matter to the soil, higher status of nutrient in soil and well development of root system and also due to sufficient release of nitrogen from dry forage of different legumes after decomposition.

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FIGURES

Fig. 1. Effect of legume mulching on N, P K and S content of V-1 tree mulberry leaf at 45 DAP

Fig. 2. Larvae obtained from double hybrid silkworms FC1 x FC2 fed with leaves of tree mulberry mulched with black gram and green gram

Tree mulberry + Black gram (T₃)

Tree mulberry+ Green gram (T₄)

Table 1: Effect of legume intercropping on plant height, shoot length and number of shoots per plant of V-1 tree mulberry at 45 and 60 DAP

Treatments	Plant height (cm)		Shoot length (cm)		Number of shoots plant ⁻¹	
	45 DAP	60 DAP	45 DAP	60 DAP	45 DAP	60 DAP
T ₁ : TM + Rice bean	216.60	253.33	141.00	169.13	20.93	22.53
T ₂ : TM + Cowpea	230.13	265.47	147.87	179.27	22.13	23.93

T₃: TM + Black gram	255.80	281.40	167.60	190.53	23.87	25.60
T₄: TM + Green gram	246.73	276.00	155.40	183.53	22.60	24.20
T₅: TM + Horse gram	225.53	251.07	136.27	161.40	19.73	21.47
T₆: TM + Field bean	235.80	264.13	145.67	173.67	21.73	23.73
T₇: Sole tree mulberry	211.53	237.80	132.60	158.87	19.07	20.93
F – test	*	*	*	*	*	*
S. Em±	2.763	4.634	1.185	0.924	0.486	0.344
C. D. @ 5 %	8.515	14.280	3.652	2.848	1.496	1.060

Note: * Significant at 5 %, TM – Tree mulberry, DAP: Days after pruning

Table 2: Effect of legume mulching on number of leaves per plant of V-1 tree mulberry at 45, 60 and yield at 60 DAP

Treatments	Number of leaves plant ⁻¹		Yield ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹ (tonnes)
	45 DAP	60 DAP	60 DAP
T₁: TM + Rice bean	265.73	364.33	67.41
T₂: TM + Cowpea	278.60	374.93	77.49
T₃: TM + Black gram	295.47	391.93	83.42
T₄: TM + Green gram	285.27	387.27	79.16
T₅: TM + Horse gram	263.67	360.60	59.57
T₆: TM + Field bean	270.93	368.93	68.98
T₇: Sole tree mulberry	212.07	356.40	50.39
F – test	*	*	*
S. Em±	6.856	5.314	2.762
C. D. @ 5 %	21.125	16.376	8.512

Note: * Significant at 5 %, TM – Tree mulberry, DAP: Days after pruning

Table 3: Influence of legume mulching on N, P, K, Ca, Mg, S and crude protein contents of V-1 tree mulberry leaves at 45 DAP

Treatments	Nitrogen (%)	Phosphorous (%)	Potassium (%)	Calcium (%)	Magnesium (%)	Sulphur (%)	Crude protein (%)
T ₁ : TM + Rice bean	3.84	0.40	1.40	0.70	0.52	0.54	24.14
T ₂ : TM + Cowpea	3.94	0.43	1.79	1.28	0.68	0.71	24.68
T ₃ : TM + Black gram	4.28	0.56	2.93	1.02	0.57	0.85	26.60
T ₄ : TM + Green gram	4.02	0.49	2.75	0.93	0.56	0.72	25.39
T ₅ : TM + Horse gram	3.67	0.34	1.56	0.61	0.45	0.50	23.13
T ₆ : TM + Field bean	3.88	0.41	1.68	1.22	0.60	0.69	24.06
T ₇ : Sole tree mulberry	3.27	0.31	1.24	0.53	0.41	0.38	19.28
F – test	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
S. Em±	0.037	0.007	0.028	0.015	0.008	0.007	0.149
C. D. @ 5 %	0.113	0.022	0.087	0.045	0.026	0.020	0.459

Significant at 5 %, TM – Tree mulberry, DAP: Days after pruning

Table 4: Larval weight, cocoon weight and pupal weight of silkworm in relation to legume mulching in tree mulberry

Treatments	Fifth instar larval weight (g/10 larvae) (5 th day)	Cocoon weight (g / 10 cocoons)	Pupal weight (g / 10 pupae)
T ₁ : Tree mulberry + Rice bean	39.50	23.29	18.06
T ₂ : Tree mulberry + Cowpea	39.20	24.23	18.61
T ₃ : Tree mulberry + Black gram	41.73	26.01	19.69
T ₄ : Tree mulberry + Green gram	39.92	25.09	19.24
T ₅ : Tree mulberry + Horse gram	38.24	21.20	16.44
T ₆ : Tree mulberry + Field bean	38.71	23.01	17.63
T ₇ : Sole tree mulberry	37.22	21.05	16.37
F – test	*	*	*
S. Em±	0.477	0.308	0.223
C. D. @ 5 %	1.471	0.948	0.687

TM – Tree mulberry * - significant

Table 5: Effect of legume mulching on cocoon shell weight, cocoon shell ratio, single cocoon filament length and filament denier after legume mulching in tree mulberry

Treatments	Cocoon shell weight (g / 10 shells)	Cocoon shell ratio (%)	Single cocoon filament length (m)	Filament denier
T ₁ : Tree mulberry + Rice bean	5.06	21.74	1025.10	2.89
T ₂ : Tree mulberry + Cowpea	5.48	22.62	1083.75	2.92
T ₃ : Tree mulberry + Black gram	6.12	23.53	1277.17	3.53
T ₄ : Tree mulberry + Green gram	5.71	22.75	1202.40	3.34
T ₅ : Tree mulberry + Horse gram	4.64	21.87	1044.90	2.98
T ₆ : Tree mulberry + Field bean	5.19	22.54	1035.90	3.34
T ₇ : Sole tree mulberry	4.43	21.06	1016.10	2.95
F – test	*	*	*	*
S. Em±	0.074	0.064	17.216	0.149
C. D. @ 5 %	0.227	0.196	53.031	0.459

TM – Tree mulberry * - significant